

THE PROCESS OF INSTABILITY IN CREATIVE THINKING**"Silk Road" international university of tourism and cultural heritage****Ass. Prof. (PhD) Boynazarov Odiljon Faizullayevych****E-mail: odiljon.boynazarov@univ-silkroad.uz****Abstract**

This article discusses the nature and specificity of creative thinking. The article examines the instability aspects of creative thinking. In the process of evolutionary development, the system of creative thinking of the individual society has been philosophically analyzed.

Key words: creativity, creative thinking, instability, factors, imagination, coincidence.

It is no secret that new ideas and a new way of thinking lead to renewal of life. The place of creative thinking in the life of society is incomparable. The formation of a new worldview in every sphere accelerates the development of the state. This is shown by the historical processes themselves. Creativity is very simple, but at the same time, it is gaining complexity, which comes from the mental potential and thinking ability of a person. The history of the origin of creativity, the fact that this word was created long before the period of scientific criticism and its relevance today will be the focus of our research today.

Before thinking about creativity, let's explore the meaning of this word, the word "Creative" is derived from English, and "creative" literally means "new creation, creative creation". means meanings. Summarizing these concepts, we can give the following definition: Creative thinking is the leadership of the mind, making decisions quickly and without hesitation, loyalty to the task and field, flexibility of thinking, unconventionality, not shying away from non-standard decisions and solutions, consciousness, thinking and a process that depends on purposeful education and formation of features such as training the mind to see and understand the perspective in all directions, to be able to forecast. [1.7] Also, creative thinking is the speed of thinking, making independent decisions, making good use of a situation of instability, and building confidence in one's own abilities.

P. Torrens defines creative thinking as the manifestation of sensitivity to problems, the lack or inconsistency of existing knowledge. [2.58] Sensations are an unstable mental process.

Creativity is a person's ability to create new ideas, alternatives, solutions and opportunities in a unique and unconventional way. [3.113]

Creativity is the ability to imagine something unpredictable, original and unique. It should be expressive, exciting and creative. This is a reflection of how well a person can think in any situation.

Therefore, creativity is more a result of a mental process that takes place in an unstable way in thinking.

Owners of unusual creative thinking are relentlessly sought after with their unique methods to realize their destiny [4. 13]. So, creative thinking is a mental process that is unstable in the successful creation of new knowledge.

Kreativlik - o'zini namoyon qilishi mumkin bo'lgan ijodiy fikrlash, his qilish, muloqot qilish va shaxsni bir butun sifatida xarakterlash va ushbu shaxs faoliyatining mahsuli. Guilford firicha: "Kreativlik - bu turli xil fikrlash jarayonidir" [5. 87]. Creativity is inventive thinking, feeling, communicating and characterizing a person as a whole, which can manifest itself and is a product of the activity of this person. According to Guilford: "Creativity is a process of different thinking" [5. 87]. So, J. Guilford, one of the founders of the theory of creativity, defined the six dimensions of creativity as the ability to solve non-standard problems, semantic flexibility, that is, the ability to see new features in an object, find new uses for them, and define an unstable process. Emphasized.

Creativity is communication in the process of thinking, feeling, overcoming stagnation. A creative person is always more tolerant of others: he is ready to admit that his usual behavior may not be the most and performs the most optimal, but it is performed only according to the principle; everyone has a different worldview and sees the world in their own way, independently, and people do not want to be controlled by their loved ones who surround them. [6. 114] Creative thinking is the result of a linear process of instability.

Creativity as a personality-developing category is an integral part of human thinking and spirituality, it is not in the multifaceted nature of the knowledge a person has, but in the pursuit of new ideas, established stereotypes (known and generally accepted it is manifested in reforming and changing the ideas, making unexpected and unusual decisions in the process of solving life problems. That is, creativity cannot be achieved by repeating the given knowledge, the main condition is the emergence of a new thought, a new idea in the process of creative thinking. For example, even if you memorized English words and "drank down" the rules of grammar, if you can't write an essay, it's all useless. Therefore, imagination plays an important role in the process of creative thinking. This is exactly what Albert Einstein meant when he said, "Imagination is more important than knowledge." Often, unusual ideas and solutions come to a

person's mind unexpectedly. For this, first of all, it is necessary to put an end to the sameness and routine in the process of thinking.

Indifference to coincidences can sometimes become a problem in the formation of creative thinking. We all know that many inventions are made in emergency and accidental situations. It can be in the form of the apple that fell on Isaac Newton's head, the scientist Alexander Fleming, the scientist who discovered the antibiotic, which was left unwashed and became moldy.

To sum up, it is necessary to enrich the minds of young people with the knowledge, skills and abilities gained about the theoretical foundations of the formation of creative thinking among young people, to gain self-confidence in creativity, and to stimulate curiosity and research. When a person puts his brain in "extreme" and "difficult" "unstable" situations and situations, creativity comes out of the shell as a result. Creative thinking is deepened by unstable situations. The process of formation of creative thinking is a long-term, continuous and unstable process, the most important stage of which is the educational period. The unstable aspects of creative thinking are manifested in new inventions, new thoughts, spiritual upliftment, inspiration and new ideas.

References:

1. Yusupova G. "Yoshlarda kreativ tafakkur va maqsadga erishishga nisbatan ishonch hissini shakllantirishning samaradorligi". T., 2014. - B. 7.
2. Aksenova V.I., Karandashova R.G. Talaba shaxsining erkin rivojlanishi: Ta'limning falsafiy va psixologik-pedagogik asoslari. M.: 2001. - B. 52-59.
3. Sultanova G.S. Kreativlik va innovatsiya: umumiylik va farq.// Imom Buxoriy saboqlari. 2020. 3-son. Samarqand., 2020 - B. 113-114.
4. 4. Teresa M. Amabayl. Creative thinking in business / Per. English — M.: Alpina Business Book's. Series "Classic Harvard Business Review". 2006. - C. 228.
5. Guilford J. Scholarly articles for Guilford J. Creativity. 1950. - P. 87.
6. 6. Khrustalev Yu.M. Philosophy (Metafizicheskie nachala kreativnogo myshleniya) M. , 2015. – S. 114.